

ACCOUNTING FOR THE EFFECTS OF OPERATIONAL RISK MANAGEMENT PRACTICE ON DIVIDEND POLICY PAYOUT OF A CORPORATE FIRM IN NIGERIA. EVIDENCE FROM BANKS

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<p>Keyword: Deposit money banks, Operational Risk Management, Dividend policy payout</p>	<p>Abstract: Nigerian deposit money banks function to actively participate in the financial stimulations of the economy. It accepts deposits from customers, manages it, serves as trustee and credits it to their account on demand. This study examined the effect of operational Risk Management on Dividend policy payout of banks in Nigeria. Its specific objective is: to determine the effect of Liquidity risk ratio on earnings per share selected banks in Nigeria between 2014 and 2025. The research design adopted was ex post facto. Secondary data for the variables were obtained from audited annual reports and accounts of ten (8) deposit money banks out of the thirty-five (35) deposit money banks quoted on the Nigeria Exchange Group for the respective years. Panel regression fixed effect model adopted for data analysis using Cross-section random Hausman Test, which is crucial for determining the appropriate panel data estimation technique. The Hausman Test is used to decide between fixed effects and random effects models by evaluating whether there is a significant difference between the two models' estimates. The result indicated that liquidity risk ratio has positive but not statistically significant effect with $PV = 0.0918$, Coefficient = 28.28475 on Earnings per share of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The implications are that variations in Liquidity Risk may affect shareholders earnings but the effect is not substantial enough to be considered significant at conventional levels. Based on the finding, It was concluded that operational risk management through liquidity risk management ensure that earning per share of shareholders are improved. On the bases of this, it was recommended among others that banks should carefully manage their lending practices, diversify their lending opportunities and match loan growth with risk management to maximize shareholders returns. Also, it was</p>
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recommended that banks should still manage their lending practices carefully. Increasing the LAR alone may not substantially affect EPS

1.0 Introduction

Nigerian banks engage in operational risk by extension in order to let the cash deposited with them generate profit as no idle cash does that. Catherine (2020) posits that credit as part of the operations attracts demands for the bank services. This became necessary because interplay of the bank sectors and the beneficiaries of its services is the reason for active growing economy. The banks benefit as income realizable from its lending activities is ploughed back an investment to boost its operations. Kaaya (2023) asserts that profit arising from increased sales over added costs of receivables. Influences the profit which can be used in different ventures of the bank to sustain its operations. Among which is credit extension to demanding and deserved customers.

Operational risk extension entails legitimate possession of goods or services, cash in this case under agreement to pay at a later date. When finance is loaned, payment of principal and interest is made in bulk or installment at a stipulated or streamed intervals until the total sum is repaid. Such extension sometimes are prone to defaults and delinquencies. Defaults arises when a borrower fails to pay out rightly and become delinquent when payment is made

not as at when due. When this happens, credit risk sets in. This type of risk is primarily that of deposit banks which after thought and due assessments of the borrower(s) extended the loan. Adegbie & Otitolaye (2020) affirms that credit risk of deposit money banks are on increase in numerous financial instruments other than loan such as acceptances, trade financing, interbank transactions, foreign exchange transactions, swaps, etc. It leads to low cash flow, low liquidity levels and financial distress of the bank(s). Evidence from studies suggested that operational risk entails a situation where a borrower of fund or any other debt with default in payment that he or she is obliged to do. Awareness of credit risk aids deposit money banks to adjust their capital and be conscious of market situation bearing in mind that other parties may default. As such managers are advised to employ most recent modern risk management techniques such as risk appraisal, diversification and control to enhance the earning capacity of the banks (Catherine, 2020). These they can undertake order process whereby risks with highest loss and highest livelihood of occurrence are first brought under control before the ones with lesser possibility of occurrence and

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lesser loss are controlled in descending order. All these rigidities is termed as operational risk management which under this study is measured by the extent of liquidity risks banks take in their operations.

Furthermore, Risk diversification explains the spreading of investments into a broader range of financial service areas such as businesses, credit cards, mortgage, etc. The main objective is to increase returns by investing in various lucrative areas that would yield higher and long term returns thereby making the banks more liquid.

While risk control also known as hazard control emphasizes a process of ensuring that loans are given to those customers that have capability of timely payment. Precisely, it involves implementing measures to reduce the likelihood or impact of potential risks. Sound credit risk management practices if employed by deposit money banks can lead to long-term viability, job creation, competitiveness and long-term poverty eradication, live improvement as well as economic viability, (Siyانبola & Adebayo, 2021). It therefore suggests that managers should adequately identify, assess, and mitigate (prevent) potential risks associated with extending credits. While credit extension can result in default, it can also result in delinquency. Earnings of shareholders in deposits money banks is measured by earnings per share (EPS). Earnings per share represents the banks net

income from operations divided by its outstanding shares of common stock. It is a key metric determinant while trying to ascertain shareholders portion of bank profit. This net income is a balance income available to shareholders after removal cost and expenses. (Adesugba, and Olalere, 2022).

In conclusion, a number of studies have been conducted on operational risk management and earnings in different directions. Since knowledge keeps on unveiling, more research is needed to take up the variables in a peculiar dimension. Thus, this primarily it focused on examining the effect of the dependent variable Earning Per Share on the independent variables and Liquidity Risk Ratio towards enhancing the earnings of the respective shareholders

As a result of these incessant failures (defaults and delinquencies), the deposit money banks developed credit risk management scheme to minimize loan default. Hence this study dwells on how to discover whether proper management of operational risk management metrics can significantly improve bank operations and consequently enhanced shareholders earnings of the banks. Appraise effect of liquidity ratio on earnings per share of shareholders of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Other areas of this work will continue with review of related Literature which comprises of conceptual review, theoretical review and

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empirical review and will be concluded with identification of knowledge gap. Others include the methodology which includes the research design and model specification, Next is the data presentation and Analysis which includes the data presentation and Analysis which concludes with findings, Discussion of findings, Result implication, conclusions, recommendations and finally contribution to knowledge in the world knowledge.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE CONCEPTUAL REVIEW; OPERATIONAL RISK MANAGNMENT;

Operational risk management entails probability of loss in business ventures caused by operational technicalities of the management which has a likelihood of a negative outcome (Catherine, 2020). Owualla, (2020), defines Operational risk management by referring to loss or exposure to unfavorable business outcomes arising from variation between expected and actual outcome of interest resources arising from how the management manages the short- and long-term obligations of the firm.. It is a term that explains that borrower will default in making payment which it is obliged to do. Credit risk is a practice of identifying, assessing and mitigating potential risks associated with extending credits to individuals, businesses and other entities. It therefore involves evaluating the likelihood of borrower's default and

determining appropriate measures to reduce the impact of such risk in the operational process. Key operations of deposit money banks involve lending which also involves inherent risk of loan losses but cannot be avoided due to its benefits of charges such as charging premium for the risk-taking activities and earning of profits.

Adegbie and Otitolaye (2020) assert that banks are increasingly facing credit risk in various financial instruments other than loans, bonds, equities, acceptances, trade financing etc. Undertaking credit risk leads to possibility of loss as well as profit opportunity. As such, there is tendency for good credit risk management in the management of the bank's operational activities.

MEASURES OF OPERATIONAL RISK MANAGNMENT Liquidity Risk Ratio (LRR)

Ezema, and Okere (2025) defines liquidity risk ratio as the ratio between current assets (Liquid resources of the company) and current liabilities (short – term debts). It measures the ability of the deposit money banks to meet upcoming debt payment with the most liquid part of its assets (cash at hand and short-term investments). It ascertains the ability of debtors to pay current debt obligations internally without raising external capital. Evidences from Udenwa et al (2023) indicates that it is calculated by dividing total current assets by total current liabilities.

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That is: Liquidity risk ratio: $\frac{\text{Total current assets}}{\text{Total current liabilities}} \times 100\%$

Total current liabilities

MEASURE OF EARNIG CAPACITY OF DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS

Earnings Capacity (EC); This in business context is the expected earnings, arising from maximizing the expected present value of future actual earnings. Fixed assets of commercial banks help to increase the earning capacity by providing efficient product output. Enyi (2018) asserts that the justification of using the total operating costs for the basis of determining a firm's earning capacity was based on the premise that an investor expects returns income on the value of his initial investments and not on the investment plus the expected returns which a firm's turnover or total income generally represents.

Earnings Per Share (EPS); Udenwa et al (2023) stated that this is the ratio between a company's earnings and the number of common shares outstanding to each share of common stock. It is the value of earnings per outstanding share of common stock of a company and as well the proportion of a company's income made available to shareholders that are allocated to each outstanding shares of common stock. It therefore indicates the bank's profitability by showing how much money the bank(s) make (s) for each share of its stock. It is useful in

measuring a company's current financial standing and also past performance. (Babatunde et al, 2023).

Practically, Earnings Per Share (EPS) = $\frac{\text{Net income} - \text{preferred dividend}}{\text{Average outstanding common shares}}$

Average outstanding common shares

Evidence proved that average outstanding common shares is used because it gives accurate earning since companies may issue or buy back stock throughout the year and that makes the actual outstanding shares and true earnings per share difficult to calculate, (Babatunde et al, 2023)

Deposit Money Bank (DMB); Abdulrahman, (2021) stated that banks existence in the business sector has unavoidably continued to play a crucial role in the development of Nigeria economy. This is outstanding as banks simultaneously satisfy the needs and preferences of surplus and deficit units.

Aregban, (2023) deposit money banks are to function to serve in creation of money, payment mechanism, pooling of savings, extension of credits, financing of foreign trade, trust service, safekeeping of valuables and brokerage services. Examples of deposit money banks in Nigeria are Zenith bank Plc, Fidelity Bank Plc, Union Bank Plc, Access Bank Plc. etc. all quoted on Nigeria exchange group.

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Alalade et al (2020) expressed that Nigeria deposit money banks have been strained by the deteriorating quality of its credit asset subject to significant dip in equity market indices, global oil prices, and sudden depression of Naira against global currencies (BGL banking report, 2010

Theoretical Framework; Liquidity Management Theory

This theory was propounded by Lord Keynes in 1936 and proposed by H. G. Moulton who states that if the deposit money banks continue a substantial amount of assets that can be moved to other banks for cash without any loss of material in case of necessity, then there is no need to rely on maturities. Besides, irrespective of the nature and feature of a borrower's business, the bank plans the liquidation of the term loan from the expected income of the borrower. The bank can attend to their liability obligations by borrowing in the money and capital markets. They can bid in the markets for additional funds to meet loan demands as well as deposit withdrawals. Liquidity management precisely, entails injecting into circulation an amount of money or liquidity in accordance with the expected level of short-term reserve money without distorting the operations of the corporate firm (Andrew and Osuji, 2013). It is very essential for Deposit money banks to maintain a strong liquidity management competency in order to continuously play

essential intermediation roles in financial system and as well as enjoy a positive return on investment of their financial resources (Nwankwo, 2014). This attests that liquidity managerial skill is very relevant due to the fact that there is always a trade-off between liquidity and profitability. Profitability falls if banks tie down excess liquidity that would have been profitably invested. Ugwu et al (2020) opines that strong liquidity management procedures can improve bank's reputation, translate into higher equity returns and as well shareholders earnings. Besides, it equally suggests to investors that the bank is strong enough to withstand any potential reforms in anticipation of distress. The basic contribution of the theory is consideration of both sides of a bank's statement of financial position as source of liquidity. If active liability moderates well the effect of financial risk, liquidity risk particularly the negative risks is reduced to a barest minimum thereby tending towards high profitability of such banks that can now yield commensurately to shareholders fund or investment. This study is therefore anchored on the above theory because always had a trade-off operational activity between liquidity and profitability.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Dibua and Ikilidih (2023) evaluated the effect of debt, ratio on earnings per share of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Data were

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extracted from annual reports and accounts of the selected 21 firms studied between 2010 and 2020. Panel least square (PLS) regression analysis and Hausman test were used to test hypothesis. The result showed that there is a significant and positive relationship between debt ratio and earnings per share (EPS).

David and Muhammad (2023) in addition examined the effect of earnings per share, current ratio, and debt to equity ratio on stock prices before and during the Covid - 19 pandemic with price earning ratio as a moderating variable. Multiple regression technique was used to test the secondary data to discover that earnings per share and price earning ratio have a positive effect on stock prices before and during the Covid – 19 pandemic. Current ratio had no effect on share prices before and during Covid – 19 pandemic. Debt to equity ratio negatively affected stock prices before the pandemic while no effect during the pandemic.

Biswas et al (2024) examined loan loss provisions and income smoothing in banks: the role of trade openness and FIRS in Brics nations 2014 – 2020. To test hypothesis, fixed effect and two – step system panel generalized methods of Moments (GMM) estimator was used. Findings was that trade openness (TO) positively affects income smoothing (earning management) across Brics commercial banks and indication from

path analysis is that such effect is driven by nonperforming loans.

Umar et al (2022) undertook a study on the effect of credit risk on financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Data sourced from published accounts of 14 of such banks where analyzed using multiple regression analysis and result revealed that loan loss provision (LLP) and capital adequacy ratio (CAR) have direct and significant relationship with return on equity (ROE) while nonperforming loan ratio (NPLR) and total asset to total deposit (TATD) have significant effect on return on equity (ROE).

Ezu et al (2023) appraised the effect of capital adequacy on the financial performance of Nigerian deposit money banks for the period 2000 – 2020. Data were sourced from audited annual publications financial statements of all deposit money banks on the Nigeria stock exchange. Analysis was by ordinary least square multiple regression. Results indicated that total capital to risk weighted assets, banks capitalization to total credits and debt in equity ratio had direct and inverse linear significant effect on return on asset (ROA).

Ihejiroka and Ojiegbe (2024) studied capital adequacy and return on equity of deposit money banks in Nigeria from 2004 to 2022. Data were gathered from NDIC annual financial statistical bulletin and subjected to inferential test. The

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result revealed that total qualifying capital has significant influence on return on equity capital to risk weighted ratio has statistically significant and positive relationship to return on equity and capital adequacy has significant effect on return on equity of deposit money banks in Nigeria

Babatunde et al (2023) evaluated risk management and performance of deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. A re-examination emphasis on panel data analysis on secondary data from annual reports of the various banks studied. It found that both liquidity and capital risk variables exert a negative but insignificant effect on performance of the internationally authorized banks positively and significantly.

In furtherance, Udenwa et al (2023) investigated the effect of liquidity risk on the financial performance of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. Ratio of loans and advances to total assets and the ratio of loans and advances to total deposits were specific variables used to measure liquidity risk whereas return on asset (ROA) was specific variable used to measure financial performance. Data were from annual reports of the various deposit money banks under study that were listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NEG) from 2014 to 2021. Results was that of panel regression analysis which revealed that the loans and advances to total assets and loans and advances to total deposit have a significant effect

on the performance of the quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Mogusu et al (2022) investigated the effect of liquidity risk on shareholders wealth of commercial banks listed on the Nigeria stock exchange (NSE) between 2013 and 2019. Data were sourced from published financial statements and banking survey publications and analyzed using simple and multiple regression analysis. The result showed that liquidity risk had a negative effect on shareholders wealth.

Over the years between 2006 and 2019 Jacob et al (2022) examined the effect of liquidity risk management on the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Data were gathered from annual reports and accounts of the selected banks and analyzed using STATA 13. It revealed that both total deposits to total assets and total loan to total deposit have negative insignificant effect on return on asset (ROA). Conversely, liquidity assets to total assets and short-term liabilities to liquid assets both have a negative significant effect on the return on asset (ROA) of the sampled banks.

Eyon (2025) determined the effect of liquidity risk on financial performance of Ethiopian commercial banks. A decision to carry out a balanced fixed effect panel regression was undertaken on secondary data sourced from annual reports and accounts for the period 2007 – 2024. It was observed that liquidity coverage

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ratio, net stable funding ratio, loan to deposit ratio and liquidity ratio had negative and statistically significant impact on the bank's financial performance while cash reserve ratio, portion of nonperforming loan, Gross domestic product (GDP), growth rate had negative and insignificant impact on financial performance and liquidity risk negatively affects financial performance.

Alalade et al (2025) conducted research on the effect of liquidity on financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria between 2009 and 2018. Secondary data extracted from annual reports employed panel regression analysis with emphasis on pooled, fixed and random effect model. Findings were that liquidity risk had positive and significant effects on return on equity (ROE), return on asset (ROA) and earnings per share.

KNOWLEDGE GAP

In the above empirical reviewed works, it is evident that none of the authors to the best of my knowledge researched vividly on the above study bearing earning per share as the measure of shareholders earnings. While others used deposit bank performance, this study dwell on shareholders earnings not on profitability in Nigeria particularly within the period 2014 to 2025. Besides, the models of the study provided strong empirical validation considered to significant to proxy these specific independent

variables: Liquidity risk ratio, with specific dependent variable, Earning per share (EPS). As such it has added to knowledge having extended the study for this reasonable period.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The design that was adopted for this study was *ex-post facto* research design. According to Tuckman (1972) the term *ex-post facto* is an experiment in which the researcher examines the effects of a naturalistically-occurring treatment after that treatment has occurred rather than creating the treatment itself. The researcher considered the design most suitable to this study in as much as it determines the cause –and-effect relationship between independent variables (Liquidity Risk Ratio) and dependent variable (Earning Per Share). Besides, the treatment is included by selection rather than manipulation.

Model Specification

The model specification is designed to examine the a linear regression framework, allowing us to assess how these independent variables influence EPS, taking into account both the magnitude and direction of their effects. Specifically, the model specification considers the Fixed Effects Model (FEM) and Panel EGLS Multiple Regression to control for individual heterogeneity across banks and ensure robust estimates. It was accomplished through this

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regression model that relates “Y” to a function of “X” and β the unknown parameter.

Thus: $Y = f(X, \beta)$, Where: Y= Dependent Variable, F = function of, X = Independent Variable β = Coefficient of independent or explanatory variables. This gave window for adopting a similar model based on the study of Udenwa et al (2023) investigated the effect of liquidity risk on the financial performance of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. Ratio of loans and advances to total assets and the ratio of loans and advances to total deposits were specific variables used to measure liquidity risk whereas return on asset (ROA)

Thus: $ROE = f(CAR + LAR + DR + BS + GR + \beta)$

Such that: ROE = Return on Equity, F = function of, = Capital Adequacy Ratio
LAR = Loan and Advance Ratio, DR = Debt Ratio, BS = Bank Size

GR = Growth rate, β = unknown parameter

Therefore, $EPS = f(LADR + LLPR + NPLR + CAR + LRR + \beta)$

In substitute we have the fixed effects account for time-invariant characteristics within the data, while the random effects model serves as a basis for comparison, determined through the Hausman test. The functional model is now specified as:

Thus, $EPS = f(LRR)$

(Equation 1)

The model used a linear regression equation stated below to test the hypotheses. They are:

$EPS_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LRR_{it} + c_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$

(Equation 2)

Where; EPS = Earnings Per Share, LRR = Liquidity risk ratio, β_0 is the constant term or intercept for firm i in the year t . β_1 is linear regression coefficients to be estimated. c_{it} is the non-observable individual effect while ε_{it} is the disturbance or error term for firm i in the year t . In comparison; $ROE = f(CAR + LAR + DR + BS + GR + \beta)$, $EPS = f(LRR)$. Based on the specification LAR were similarly undertaken as the variables of independent variable.

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A Priori Expectations

Liquidity Risk Ratio (+) (LRR)	Positive	Effective liquidity management allows the bank to meet obligations without strain, supporting profitability, shareholders earnings and other operational rigidity and boosting EPS.
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Source: Researcher's Arrangement, 2026

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Data Presentation; Panel Data Extracted from Audited Annual Reports and Accounts of the Individual Banks

BANKS	YEAR	EPS	LRR
Access	2014	114	1.24718
Access	2015	174	1.322591
Access	2016	221	1.437619
Access	2017	177	1.434595
Access	2018	254	1.16243
Access	2019	207	1.011129
Access	2020	225	1.069465
Access	2021	314	0.631727
Access	2022	469	0.640503
Access	2023	1507	0.61829
Access	2024	469	0.640503
Access	2025	1507	0.61829
FCMB	2014	0.27	0.842168
FCMB	2015	0.13	1.158035
FCMB	2016	0.19	1.003539
FCMB	2017	0.08	1.158035
FCMB	2018	0.18	0.842168
FCMB	2019	0.18	0.060891
FCMB	2020	0.15	0.04802
FCMB	2021	0.26	0.101565
FCMB	2022	0.37	0.128125

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FCMB	2023	0.97	0.018627
FCMB	2024	0.37	0.128125
FCMB	2025	0.97	0.018627
Fidelity	2014	48	0.653756
Fidelity	2015	48	0.761592
Fidelity	2016	34	0.731739
Fidelity	2017	65	0.730724
Fidelity	2018	79.16	0.760464
Fidelity	2019	94	0.450633
Fidelity	2020	92	0.533707
Fidelity	2021	79	0.671121
Fidelity	2022	161	0.588205
Fidelity	2023	311.04	0.690113
Fidelity	2024	161	0.588205
Fidelity	2025	311.04	0.690113
FirstBank	2014	13	1.260806
FirstBank	2015	27	1.34083
FirstBank	2016	21	1.223006
FirstBank	2017	26	1.235783
FirstBank	2018	26	1.14619
FirstBank	2019	39	1.089032
FirstBank	2020	94	1.100435
FirstBank	2021	36	1.115598
FirstBank	2022	54	1.140403
FirstBank	2023	42	0.430843
FirstBank	2024	54	1.140403
FirstBank	2025	42	0.430843
GTBank	2014	3.03	1.133153
GTBank	2015	3.2	1.224903
GTBank	2016	4.31	1.176971

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GTBank	2017	5.39	1.212315
GTBank	2018	5.67	1.086433
GTBank	2019	5.95	1.089985
GTBank	2020	6.05	0.951619
GTBank	2021	0.28	0.530168
GTBank	2022	3.01	0.652625
GTBank	2023	3.62	0.545207
GTBank	2024	3.01	0.652625
GTBank	2025	3.62	0.545207
Stanbic	2014	131	1.883556
Stanbic	2015	99	1.841026
Stanbic	2016	6	2.060953
Stanbic	2017	250	2.052666
Stanbic	2018	151	2.095762
Stanbic	2019	321	2.060004
Stanbic	2020	237	3.050349
Stanbic	2021	16.1	3.175641
Stanbic	2022	138	2.946302
Stanbic	2023	275	2.82721
Stanbic	2024	138	0.32238
Stanbic	2025	275	0.296713
Sterling	2014	42	0.32238
Sterling	2015	36	0.296713
Sterling	2016	18	0.263643
Sterling	2017	14.9	0.273304
Sterling	2018	33	0.348541
Sterling	2019	37	0.454399
Sterling	2020	39	0.388357
Sterling	2021	52	0.465817
Sterling	2022	67	0.515745
Sterling	2023	48	0.516359

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Sterling	2024	67	0.515745
Sterling	2025	48	0.516359
UBA	2014	1.08	1.227883
UBA	2015	1.11	1.079657
UBA	2016	1.14	1.11246
UBA	2017	1.17	1.046925
UBA	2018	1.2	0.9614
UBA	2019	37	1.298365
UBA	2020	37	1.143667
UBA	2021	27.2	0.731661
UBA	2022	10.9	0.746978
UBA	2023	20.7	0.737898
UBA	2022	10.9	0.746978
UBA	2023	20.7	0.737898

Author's compilation 2025

The trend of the data;

Liquidity Risk Ratio (LRR): LRR's effect on EPS is mixed across the banks. For some, like Stanbic bank and GTBank, higher LRR is linked with stable or rising EPS, indicating that efficient recovery processes strengthen earnings. Conversely, in FCMB, fluctuating LRR values do not consistently translate to improved EPS, likely due to other offsetting risk factors in loan portfolios.

Log of Net Total Assets (LNTA): LNTA shows a positive effect on EPS, reflecting that banks with larger asset bases tend to generate higher earnings. Access Bank demonstrates this trend, where consistent growth in LNTA aligns with substantial increases in EPS from 2019 to 2025.

Similarly, FCMB's slow but steady growth in LNTA eventually results in better EPS figures in later years. This indicates that asset growth positively affects profitability.

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Null Hypothesis: The variable has a unit root

At Level

		EPS	LRR
With Constant	t-Statistic	0.9996	0.2385
	Prob.	0.1630	0.9541
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	0.8560	0.3582
	Prob.	0.2021	0.3394
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	0.9945	0.5905
	Prob.	0.6168	0.2140

At First Difference

		d(EPS)	d(LRR)
With Constant	t-Statistic	0.9529	0.0404
	Prob.	0.0099	0.4519
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	0.8105	0.1603
	Prob.	0.0493	0.7686
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	0.8417	0.0024
	Prob.	0.0004	0.0095

Source: E-views 10 software, 2026

Earnings Per Share (EPS): The results for EPS from the ADF Unit Root Test indicate non-stationarity across all tested conditions. With a t-statistic of 0.9996 and a p-value of 0.1630 when a constant is included, the test fails to reject the null hypothesis of a unit root. This result

suggests that EPS is non-stationary at this level. When both a constant and a trend are included, the t-statistic decreases to 0.8560 with a p-value of 0.2021, which further supports the non-stationarity of EPS. Even without a constant or trend, the t-statistic is 0.9945 with a p-value of 0.6168, reinforcing the conclusion that EPS

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likely has a unit root and does not exhibit stationarity. These results imply that EPS may Hausman Test Result

require differencing or other transformations to achieve stationarity before further analysis.

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	8.011209	6	0.0052

Source: E-views 10 software, 2026

This table presents the results of the Hausman Test, which is crucial for determining the appropriate panel data estimation technique. The Hausman Test is used to decide between fixed effects and random effects models by evaluating whether there is a significant difference between the two models' estimates. The Hausman Test yields a Chi-Squared (Chi-Sq.) statistic of 8.011209 with 6 degrees of freedom (d.f.) and a p-value of 0.0052. The Chi-Sq. statistic measures the difference between the estimators obtained from the fixed effects model and the random effects model. Specifically, the test assesses whether the unique errors (or unobserved effects) in the random effects model are correlated with the regressors, which would indicate that the random effects model is inappropriate. A p-value of 0.0052 is notably below the conventional significance level of 0.05. This low p-value suggests strong evidence against the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the fixed and random effects estimates. Consequently, the results indicate that

the random effects model is not suitable because it fails to account for the correlation between the unobserved individual effects and the regressors. This correlation undermines the random effects model's assumptions and leads to biased estimates. Given this outcome, the fixed effects model is preferred as it appropriately controls for individual-specific effects and provides more reliable and consistent estimates. The fixed effects model accounts for the variations within each cross-sectional unit by controlling for unobserved heterogeneity, making it more robust when the assumption of no correlation between the individual effects and regressors is violated. The Hausman Test results decisively favor the fixed effects model over the random effects model for this dataset. The significant Chi-Square statistic and the low p-value underscore that the fixed effects model is more appropriate for capturing the dynamics of the data, thereby ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the estimation. This choice is essential for drawing valid conclusions and

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making informed decisions based on the analysis.

Panel EGLS Multiple Regression Result (Fixed-Effects Model)

Dependent Variable: EPS

Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
28.28475	16.60412	1.703478	0.0918
0.001660	0.001384	1.199811	0.2321

Source: E-views 10 software, 2026

This table Presents the results of the Panel EGLS (Estimated Generalized Least Squares) regression with a fixed-effects model, examining the effect of various independent variables on Earning per share. This model provides insights into how specific financial metrics influence ROA across different entities over time.

Liquidity Risk Ratio (LRR): The coefficient for LRR is 28.28475, with a t-statistic of 1.703478 and a p-value of 0.0918. While this result is not statistically significant at the conventional levels (e.g., 5%), it is close to being significant. The positive coefficient suggests that higher liquidity risk might be associated with a higher ROA, although the relationship is not definitive given the p-value.

Panel EGLS Multiple Regression Result (Fixed-Effects Model)

Dependent Variable: EPS

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LRR	28.28475	16.60412	1.703478	0.0918

Source: E-views 10 software, 2026

The p-value for the liquidity risk ratio (LRR) is 0.0918, which is greater than 0.05 but not by a large margin. Although this p-value is not low enough to be statistically significant at the 5% level, it is close, indicating a potential weak effect. The positive coefficient of 28.28475 and the moderately significant t-statistic of 1.703478 suggest that LRR could have a positive impact on

EPS, though it is not conclusive at the 5% significance level. Therefore, we fail to reject the null hypothesis, concluding that LRR does not have a statistically significant effect on the earnings per share of shareholders in deposit money banks in Nigeria. This finding suggests that while liquidity management is essential for the operational stability of banks, its direct effect on EPS may be limited. However, given

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the p-value is close to the significance threshold, LRR could have an effect under certain conditions or in conjunction with other factors.

5.0 FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

FINDINGS; The analysis suggests that the Liquidity Risk Ratio (LRR) positively affects EPS but is not statistically significant, with a coefficient of 28.28475 and a p-value of 0.0918, indicating that while liquidity risks may affect shareholder earnings, the effect is not substantial enough to be considered significant at conventional levels

IMPLICATION; The practical implications of the study's findings are significant for both bank management and policy makers. By identifying key factors affecting EPS, the research provides actionable insights for improving financial performance. This includes recommendations for enhancing credit risk management practices, ensuring adequate capital levels, and optimizing liquidity management. The study's contributions are valuable for academics and practitioners seeking to enhance the financial performance, earnings of shareholders and stability of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION; These findings emphasize the critical role of managing loan losses and non-performing loans in safeguarding shareholder

returns. Effective operational risk management practices are essential for improving EPS, whereas liquidity and capital management, though important, may not have as pronounced an effect on short-term profitability. The analysis underscores the need for banks to focus on reducing loan impairments and improving asset quality to enhance earnings per share, while also considering the broader context of regulatory requirements and market conditions that affect these credit risk management metrics.

RECOMMENDATIONS; Liquidity Risk Ratio (LRR): The Liquidity Risk Ratio (LRR) has a positive but statistically non-significant effect on EPS, suggesting that while liquidity management is important, its immediate impact on profitability is not substantial. Banks should still prioritize effective liquidity management to ensure they can meet their short-term obligations and avoid liquidity crises. Implementing robust liquidity planning and forecasting, optimizing the management of liquid assets, and diversifying funding sources are essential practices. Additionally, banks should strike a balance between maintaining sufficient liquidity and investing in high-yield assets to enhance profitability and support EPS growth.

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REFERENCE

Abdulrahman, R. M. (2021). Moderating effect of liquidity on the relationship between capital structure and profitability: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Ife social sciences review* 29 (1), 145-157.

Abimbola, O. A., Titilayo, M. O; Oluwatimileyin, A. and Adenle, O. A. (2022). Credit risk management: Implication for deposit money banks' performance in Nigeria. *Fuoye Journal of finance and contemporary issues*, 3 (2), 183-200.

Adegbe, F. F. and Otitolaiye, E. O. (2020). Credit risk and financial performance an empirical study of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *European Journal of accounting, auditing and finance research*, 8, (2), 38-58.

Andrew, O. A. and Osuji, C. C. (2013). The efficacy of Liquidity Management and Bank Performance in Nigeria. *International Review of Management and Business Research*, vol. 2 (1): Pp 223

Adesugba, A. K. and Olalere, V. D. (2022). The effect of credit risk management on financial performance of listed deposit money banks. Evidence from Nigeria.

International Journal of management and commerce innovations, 9 (2), 169-180. 33.

Alalade, Y. S; Ogbemor, P. I and Akwe, M. (2025). Liquidity risk and profitability of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Research Journal of finance and accounting*, 11 (8); 126-139.

Aregba, I. (2023). Loan management and performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. A comparative analysis. *Journal of advances in social sciences and management*, 1 (6). 46 – 56.

Babatunde, M. O., Rafiu, O. J., Olaide, O. O. (2023). Risk management and performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria: A re-examination. *Banks and bank system*, 8 (2)

Biswas, S., Bhattacharya, S. N., Jin, J. Y., Bhattacharya, M., Sadarangani, P. H. (2024). Loan loss provision and income smoothing in banks: The role of trade openness and IFRS in Brics. *China accounting and finance review* 26, (1) 76 – 101. [https://doi.org/10.1108\(CAFR-03-2023-0037](https://doi.org/10.1108(CAFR-03-2023-0037)

Ezema, Clifford Anene. (PhD), Nwankwo, Bobby- Godwin Ogbogu (Ph.D) and Agu Charles Ikechukwu (Ph.D)

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Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

- Catherine, N. (2020). Credit risk management financial performance. A case of bank Africa (UBA) Limited). *Open Journal of business and Management*, 8,30-38. <https://doc.org/10.4236/ojbm.2020.810002>
- Ugwu I. V; Ekwochi, E. A. and Ogbu, C. G. (2021). A critical study of corporate risk management committee impact on firm performance. *International journal of academic information systems research*, 5 (4), 24 – 39
- Devid, L. and Mohammed S. S. (2023). Return on assets, debt to equity ratio and earning per share impact on stock price on a property company listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange 2014 – 2018. *Advances in economics, business and management research* vol. 12, 1-5.
- Dibuah, E. C. and Ikilidih, J. N. (2023). Effect of debt ratio on earnings per share of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *International journal of research publication and reviews*, 4 (12), 2873 – 2879
- Effiong W, , and Eya, R. A. D. (2020). The effect of return on equity, earning per share and net profit margin on stock prices of banking companies listed on Indonesia stock exchange from 2018 – 2020. *Undapest international research and critics institute Journal of Humanities and social sciences*, 5 - (I), 162 – 171
- Eyon, K. (2025). Effect of liquidity risk on financial performance of Ethiopian Commercial banks. Master's thesis School of business, University of Addis Ababa University, 1- 138.
- Ezema, C.A and Okere, M.(2025) Management of credit Risk in Banks and its Growth for Sustainable Development in Africa. Evidence from Nigeria. *Newport International Journal of Current Research in Humanities and Social Sciences* 5(3) 8-18.
- Ezu, G. K., Nwanna, I. O., Eke - Jeff, O. M. (2023). Effect of capital adequacy on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International journal of Novel research in marketing management and economics*, 10 (1), 55 - 63.
- Ihejirika , H; and Ojide, E. (2024). Risk Management and the financial performance of banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of financial research*, 11 (5), 115 – 128.

Ezema, Clifford Anene. (PhD), Nwankwo, Bobby- Godwin Ogbogu (Ph.D) and Agu Charles Ikechukwu (Ph.D)

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Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

- Jacob, A. O., Rinqin, K. J. and Shuaibu, H. (2022). Liquidity risk management and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International journal of intellectual discourse (IJID)*, 5 (1), March 2022
- Kaaya, I. A. (2013). Credit risk and commercial bank performance in Tanzania. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4, 55 - 63.
- Mogusu, M. W. Nkari, I. M. and Wabwire, J. M. (2022). Effect of liquidity risk on shareholders wealth in commercial banks listed at the Nairobi Securities exchange. *Journal on environmental sustainability and advanced research*, 8, 84 – 90
- Mohammed, B. I, Nwala, M. N. and Mohammed, J. (2023). Impact of liquidity management on capital adequacy ratio of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of research and innovation in social science (IJRISS)*, 7 (12), 1762 – 1774
Doi:<https://doi.org/10.47772/DRISS.2023.7012137>
- Nwankwo. G. O. (2014). *Bank Management Principles and Practices*, Malthouse Press Ltd: Lagos
- Onyekwelu, U. L, Chukwuani, V. N, and Onyeka, V. N. (2018). Effect of liquidity on financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of economics and sustainable development*, 9 (4), 19 - 28 ISSN2222-2855 (outline).
- Siyanbola, T. T. and Adebayo, K. K. (2021). Credit risk management and financial sustainability of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of research in business and management*, 9 (6), 64-77
www.questjournals.org
- Tuckman, B. W. (1972). *Conducting educational research*. New York . Harcourt, Brace, Jovanovich.
- Udenwa I. V; Ekwochi, E. A. and Ogba, C. G. (2023). A critical study of corporate risk management committee impact on firm performance. *International journal of academic information systems research*, 5 (4), 24 – 39
- Umar, G, Tijjani, M. S. and Salisu, A. (2022). Effect of credit risk on financial performance of listed deposit money

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Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

banks in Nigeria. *Gusau International Journal of management and social sciences*, 5 (1), 49-55.

Ezema, Clifford Anene. (PhD), Nwankwo, Bobby- Godwin Ogbogu (Ph.D) and Agu Charles Ikechukwu (Ph.D)